

planted within 150 m of the light traps. Egg masses counted on 200 plants at 4, 6, and 8 wk after transplanting (WT) were correlated significantly ($r = 0.69$, $P < 0.05$) with total number of female moths caught during the 3 mo the crop was standing. Percentage deadhearts (DH) at 4, 6, and 8 WT was correlated with total number of YSB males and females during the 3-mo period ($r = 0.75$, $P < 0.05$).

At seven of the sites, we monitored DH-weekly from 3 to 9 WT. The rate of change differed significantly among seven periods based on the lunar month (F_6 , $32 = 6.53$, $P < 0.01$), with the peak occurring 24-27 d after the full moon (Fig. 1). The number of egg masses and male and female moths caught in light traps also differed among the 7 periods (F_6 , $70 = 2.66$, $P < 0.02$; F_6 , $30 = 11.5$, $P < 0.01$; F_6 , $30 = 6.51$, $P < 0.01$, respectively).

The concentration of egg masses is particularly striking: the average in the 20-23 d period was greater than the total in other periods combined (Fig. 2).

Although the delay between maximum number of female moths and maximum

1. Rate of change per week of deadhearts in experimental fields in relation to lunar phase. Bars represent 1 standard error. Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1981 wet season.

2. YSB egg masses at 3 sampling occasions and catches in light traps over 3 mo in relation to lunar phase. Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1981 wet season.

egg masses is longer than indicated by published descriptions of the YSB life cycle, the order of the peaks in number of females and eggs, and change in DH is as expected. The YSB generation length is substantially longer than that of a moth (45-55 d in the area studied), and it is unlikely that these peaks are due to synchronization of the insect's development with some external cue other than lunar phase.

Similar trends were observed in the 1982 wet season. While wider confirmation is needed, these results suggest that scouting for damage caused by YSB should be done primarily in the 2 wk after the full moon. They also indicate that catches in small kerosene light traps do reflect patterns in the development of nearby field populations, lending support to the use of these traps in wide area monitoring of rice insect pests. ■

Virulence of brown planthopper (BPH) populations collected in China

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We monitored the virulence of BPH populations collected from Hainan, Guangdong, Guangxi, and Zhejiang Provinces in Apr-Jun 1987-90. Collected insects were mass-reared on susceptible variety TN1 and tested on resistant varieties IR26 (containing resistance gene *Bph 1*) and IR36 (*Bph 1 + bph 2*). IR26 and IR36 plants were transplanted at 1 plant/pot 30 d after sowing, and each pot caged with 10 5th-instar nymphs 15-30 d after transplanting. Surviving BPHs were counted 10 d after infestation.

BPH populations collected in 1987-88 had significantly lower survival on IR26 and IR36 than on TN1 (see table). The Zhejiang population had the lowest survival on variety IR26. Survival on

variety IR26 of BPH populations collected in 1989-90 was similar to that on susceptible check TN1. Survival on variety IR36 was still obviously lower than that on susceptible check TN1.

These results indicate the virulence of BPH populations was becoming strong

enough to damage varieties containing *Bph 1*. They also show that the BPH population was shifting from biotype 1 to biotype 2. Establishment of BPH populations on resistant varieties widely cultivated in China and field damage need further surveillance. ■

Survival of BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål of different geographical populations on rice varieties. Hangzhou, China, 1987-90.

Locality	Date	Temperature (°C)	Survival (%) of 5th-instar nymphs		
			IR26	IR36	TN1
Hainan Lingshui	5-14 Sep 1987	24.9	45.0	19.0	66.0
Zhejiang Longyou			14.0	13.0	65.0
Guangdong Xinhui ^a	8-17 Sep 1987	28.8	44.0	12.0	82.0
Hainan Lingshui	5-14 Sep 1988	26.5	18.0	12.0	75.0
Zhejiang Longyou			9.0	3.0	88.0
Guangdong Xinhui ^a	26 Sep-5 Oct 1988	25.7	30.0	14.0	54.0
Hainan Lingshui	3-12 Sep 1989	24.4	54.0	18.8	67.0
Zhejiang Longyou			53.0	3.0	75.0
Zhejiang Hangzhou			55.0	10.0	62.0
Guangdong Xinhui ^a			46.0	4.2	64.0
Hainan Lingyou	30 Jun-10 Jul 1990	28.8	72.2	12.2	73.3
Guangxi Nanning	7-16 Jul 1990	30.2	65.6	7.8	64.4
Guangxi Longzhou			63.3	20.0	66.7
Zhejiang Longyou			71.1	12.2	73.3
Zhejiang Hangzhou			72.6	12.0	74.2

^aTested in Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Guangzhou, China.